

Genetic variation in susceptibility of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*-infected holm oak in the absence or presence of severe drought

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3 1 **Genetic variation in susceptibility of *Phytophthora cinnamomi*-infected**
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3 **19 Abstract**
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6 20 The evergreen oaks *Quercus ilex* and *Q. suber* are exposed to widespread *Phytophthora*
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8 21 infestation in natural forests. To restore diseased forests, deploying trees less susceptible
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10 22 to combined stress is the most promising approach. We aimed to determine whether
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12 23 drought affects the susceptibility of *Q. ilex* and *Q. suber* to *Phytophthora cinnamomi*
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14 24 (*Pc*) differently. Additionally, to provide scientific support for a genetic improvement
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16 25 programme to reduce the susceptibility of holm oak to decline, genetic variation and
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18 26 heritability in susceptibility to *P. cinnamomi* in *Q. ilex* in the absence or presence of
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20 27 drought were estimated. About 7,000 seedlings of 66 *Q. ilex* and nine *Q. suber* trees
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22 28 from the Extremadura region (Spain) were inoculated with *Pc* at age one year. The
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24 29 following year, half the experimental blocks were regularly watered and half were
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26 30 exposed to severe drought. In the absence of drought, *Q. ilex* was more susceptible than
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28 31 *Q. suber* to *Pc* (mortality 97 and 59%, respectively), but in the presence of drought after
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30 32 *Pc* infection the species were equally susceptible (~97% plant mortality). It could
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32 33 therefore be expected that under the climate change scenarios of drought predicted for
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34 34 the south of the Iberian Peninsula, *Q. suber* forests will be as vulnerable as *Q. ilex*
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36 35 forests to soil infestation by *Pc*. Significant additive genetic variation and heritability in
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38 36 the susceptibility of *Q. ilex* to combined *Pc* infection and drought were observed ($h^2 =$
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40 37 0.44 for time to death of plants), indicating that breeding for tolerance to combined
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42 38 stress is possible. Family variance component estimates of time to death in *Q. ilex* were
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44 39 highest in the presence of drought, and genetic control of susceptibility in *Q. ilex*
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46 40 decreased over time as plant stress increased. This is the first study to define a breeding
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48 41 population against combined stress in oak.
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5 43 **Keywords:** *Quercus ilex*; *Quercus suber*; drought stress; *Phytophthora cinnamomi*; oak
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7 44 decline; tree tolerance
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12 46 **Introduction**

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15 47 *Quercus ilex* (holm oak) is a dominant tree species of Mediterranean forests and the
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17 48 most abundant forest tree species in Italy, southern France, Portugal and Spain.
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19 49 Although the species is well adapted to seasonal drought (Ramírez-Valiente *et al.*
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21 50 2020), studies have increasingly reported climate change-induced decline and
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23 51 widespread mortality in *Q. ilex* forests (Natalini *et al.* 2016; Gea-Izquierdo *et al.* 2021;
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25 52 San-Eufrasio *et al.* 2021; Carluccio *et al.* 2024). Dehesa ecosystems, defined as human-
26
27 53 made woodlands characterised by a savannah-like structure occupied by scattered *Q.*
28
29 54 *ilex* and *Q. suber* (cork oak) trees, are extremely vulnerable to climate change-induced
30
31 55 decline (Herguido-Sevillano *et al.* 2017; Gea-Izquierdo *et al.* 2021; López-Ballesteros *et*
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33 56 *al.* 2023). The negative effects of climate warming and drought are exacerbated by
34
35 57 human intervention, soil erosion, lack of regeneration and the presence of virulent soil-
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37 58 borne pathogens (Brasier 1996; Camilo-Alves *et al.* 2013; Serrano *et al.* 2022). Since
38
39 59 the 1980s, *Phytophthora* species have been considered the primary causal agents of *Q.*
40
41 60 *ilex* and *Q. suber* dieback and mortality in dehesas (Brasier 1996; Martín-García *et al.*
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43 61 2015; Mora-Sala *et al.* 2019). Among the various *Phytophthora* species involved in the
44
45 62 decline of these trees, *P. cinnamomi* is the most virulent, causing fine root rot and
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47 63 reducing the ability of trees to uptake water (Solla *et al.* 2009; Sghaier-Hammami *et al.*
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49 64 2013; Redondo *et al.* 2015; Ruiz-Gómez *et al.* 2018).
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3 66 The combined effects of drought stress and *Pc* infection on dehesa ecosystems can be
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5 67 varied and multiple, depending on when these factors occur and how intense they are
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7 68 (Camilo-Alves *et al.* 2013; Ruiz-Gómez *et al.* 2018; Encinas-Valero *et al.* 2022). Based
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9 69 on the timing of the drought and *Pc* infection occurrence, the following three scenarios
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11 70 could potentially occur: (i) drought before infection; (ii) drought during infection; (iii)
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13 71 drought after infection. The first scenario was tested for *Q. ilex*. Exposure of seedlings
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15 72 to severe drought during two consecutive growing seasons increased plant mortality
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17 73 after *Pc* infection (Corcobado *et al.* 2014), but exposure of *Q. suber* seedlings to
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19 74 moderate drought for three to six weeks did not increase plant mortality after *Pc*
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21 75 infection (González *et al.* 2020). However, these studies are not comparable, due to
22
23 76 differences in plant age and the intensity and duration of drought stress in the two
24
25 77 experiments. The second scenario, drought during infection, does not occur in nature
26
27 78 because, as an oomycete, *Pc* requires free water in the soil to sporulate and infect
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29 79 (Hardham and Blackman 2018; Martínez-Arias *et al.* 2022). The third scenario seems to
30
31 80 be the most harmful for trees, because fine root mortality caused by *Pc* impairs water
32
33 81 uptake and increases tree vulnerability to drought, as suggested in the literature (Brasier
34
35 82 1996). The negative effects of severe drought on infected *Q. suber* trees have not been
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37 83 studied. In two experiments on *Q. ilex* (Maurel *et al.* 2001; Robin *et al.* 2001), *Pc*-
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39 84 infected seedlings were exposed to moderate water stress, but the reduced gas exchange
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41 85 and water uptake in infected plants mitigated the effect of the drought treatment,
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43 86 probably hindering any synergistic effect between infection and water stress except for
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45 87 leaf nitrogen content (Maurel *et al.* 2001). In two other experiments with more intense
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47 88 water stress treatments, *Q. ilex* leaves showed a significant reduction in photochemical
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49 89 efficiency, relative water content and protein content when *Pc* and water stress were
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51 90 present, indicating synergistic effects between the two stress factors (Ruiz-Gómez *et al.*
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3 91 2018; San-Eufrasio *et al.* 2021). However, plant harvesting 30 days post-inoculation
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5 92 allowed insufficient time for exposure to water stress, and plant mortality was not
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7 93 reported (Ruiz-Gómez *et al.* 2018). It is therefore necessary to conduct a study with a
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10 94 more intense and longer-lasting drought treatment.

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14 96 In field conditions, spring and summer drought can act sequentially and aggravate the
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16 97 health condition of oaks when infected by *Pc* (Corcobado *et al.* 2014). Knowing the
17
18 98 response to decline of the two main dehesa oak species is of paramount importance to
19
20 99 predict areas under severe risk and potential switches in species composition that could
21
22 100 affect their structure and function (Serrano *et al.* 2021). Although it has been shown that
23
24 101 *Q. ilex* is more susceptible than *Q. suber* to *Pc* (Robin *et al.* 1998, 2001; León *et al.*
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26 102 2017), *Q. ilex* is more drought tolerant due to its strategy of xylem resistance to
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28 103 cavitation and leaf resistance to desiccation (Ramírez-Valiente *et al.* 2020). For
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30 104 comparison purposes, studies should challenge both oak species to severe, long-lasting
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32 105 and combined stress.

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34 106
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36 107 Mitigating oak decline and restoring diseased dehesas have become high-priority tasks
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38 108 in the Iberian Peninsula. In addition to control methods such as isolating affected areas
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40 109 to avoid the spread of the pathogen (Camilo-Alves *et al.* 2013), amending soil to inhibit
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42 110 the pathogen (Rodríguez-Molina *et al.* 2021; López-Sánchez *et al.* 2022), and applying
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44 111 chemical treatments to enhance tree vigour (Solla *et al.* 2021), deploying less
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46 112 susceptible plant material is the most promising approach (Moreira *et al.* 2018;
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48 113 Martínez *et al.* 2023). Exploring genetic variation in the susceptibility of oak species to
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50 114 decline is the first step in implementing an effective tree breeding programme (White *et*
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52 115 *al.* 2007). The literature reports differential susceptibility to *Pc* in seedlings of cork oak
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3 116 (Tapias *et al.* 2008; Moreira *et al.* 2018) and holm oak (Tapias *et al.* 2005; Corcobado *et*
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5 117 *al.* 2017; Rodríguez-Romero *et al.* 2022; Martínez *et al.* 2023) from different origins
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7 118 and families. Geographic and family variability to drought has also been reported
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9 119 (Gimeno *et al.* 2009; Navarro-Cerrillo *et al.* 2018; San-Eufrasio *et al.* 2020, 2021).
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11 120 Although these studies are highly valuable, quantitative estimation of additive genetic
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13 121 variance and heritability of *Q. ilex* and *Q. suber* susceptibility to *Pc* and drought is
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15 122 lacking. Quantifying intraspecific variability at individual tree level for a trait (e.g.,
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17 123 stress tolerance) and estimating heritability are of pivotal importance for breeding
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19 124 purposes (White *et al.* 2007). It has been shown that Fagaceae tolerance to *Pc* and
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21 125 drought is under polygenic control (López-Villamor *et al.* 2018; Pfenninger *et al.* 2021),
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23 126 and therefore additive genetic variation of these traits would make breeding initiatives
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25 127 feasible (Alberto *et al.* 2013). In our case, to implement a successful genetic
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27 128 improvement programme for selecting oak genotypes tolerant to decline it is necessary
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29 129 to estimate quantitative genetic parameters of susceptibility to *Pc* in the absence or
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31 130 presence of drought.
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40 132 In this work, we aimed to (1) determine whether drought affects the susceptibility of *Q.*
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42 133 *ilex* and *Q. suber* to *Pc* differently, (2) quantify genetic variation in susceptibility to *Pc*
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44 134 in *Q. ilex* in the absence or presence of drought, and (3) obtain heritability values in
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46 135 susceptibility to *Pc* in *Q. ilex* in the absence or presence of drought. The following
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48 136 hypotheses were tested: (i) drought stress affects the susceptibility of *Pc*-infected *Q. ilex*
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50 137 and *Q. suber* seedlings differently; (ii) significant intraspecific variation of
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52 138 susceptibility to *Pc* at provenance and family levels occurs in *Q. ilex* in the absence or
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54 139 presence of drought.
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141 **Materials and methods**

142 **Plant material**

143 Plant material comprised half-sib families obtained from 66 *Quercus ilex* subsp. *ballota*
144 and nine *Q. suber* trees selected in Extremadura, central-western Spain (Figure 1; Table
145 S1). Although this region is dominated by open woodlands, it has one of the highest
146 proportions of forest area in Europe (68%). Covering $\sim 1.43 \cdot 10^6$ ha, dehesas of
147 evergreen oak trees are the most common ecosystems in Extremadura. *Quercus ilex* is
148 the most abundant tree in Extremadura dehesas, and grows alone ($1.14 \cdot 10^6$ ha) or in
149 mixed stands with *Q. suber* ($0.14 \cdot 10^6$ ha).

150
151 All 75 trees were healthy, 6-10 m tall, 40-60 cm in trunk diameter, and growing in 32
152 unhealthy dehesa forests across Extremadura (W Spain; Figure 1). Occurrence of *Pc*
153 was confirmed in most of the forests (Corcobado *et al.* 2013), and therefore the plant
154 material used is assumed to have undergone selection triggered by the pathogen. The
155 trees were selected to cover the five provenance sub-regions of *Q. ilex* (Tiétar-Norte del
156 Tajo (11a), Sierra de San Pedro-Guadalupe (11b), Montes de Toledo (11c), Tierra de
157 Barros-La Serena (11d) and Sierra Morena Occidental (11e); Jiménez *et al.* 1996;
158 Figure 1) and the three provenance regions of *Q. suber* (Sierra de San Pedro (2), Montes
159 de Toledo (3) and Sierra Morena Occidental (5); Díaz-Fernández *et al.* 1995) in
160 Extremadura. The climate is typically Mediterranean, with hot, dry summers from June
161 21 to September 20, and cold, rainy winters from December 21 to March 20. Location
162 and climate data for the trees are shown in Table S1.

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164 In November 2015, ~ 120 acorns from the 75 trees were collected and sent to a
165 greenhouse in Maceda, NW Spain (42.27° N, -7.62° W, 540 m a.s.l.). Acorns were

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3 166 immersed in a fungicide solution (2 g/L, Thiram 80GD, ADAMA Inc., Spain) for five
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5 167 minutes and those that floated were discarded as non-viable. Viable seeds were washed
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7 168 in sterile water and stored in peat at 4 °C for one month. In mid-January 2016, acorns
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9 169 were sown at 1 cm depth in 50-cell plastic root trainers. Individual cells had a volume of
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11 170 400 mL and were filled with fertilised peat (PKN1 Florava[®], Fertilex, Barcelona, pH 5-
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13 171 6). Each cell contained one seed. Germinated plants were kept in natural daylight under
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15 172 greenhouse shade that reduced solar radiation by 50%, and watered weekly with well
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17 173 water free of *Phytophthora* and *Pythium* species until they were properly established.
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24 175 **Experimental design and treatments**

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26 176 Seeds from the 75 trees were arranged in a complete block design replicated in 50
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28 177 blocks. In each block, the two species were intermixed and two seeds per tree were
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30 178 placed at random. Each block therefore comprised three root trainers (150 cells), and the
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32 179 study included 7,500 plants. When the first treatment started (soil infestation with *Pc*),
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34 180 875 seedlings had not germinated or were absent. The final plant material available
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36 181 comprised 6,625 plants representing circa 90 seedlings per family.
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42 183 In June 2016 (Figure 2), when plants were 12.8 ± 4.2 cm (mean \pm standard deviation)
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44 184 tall, they were soil-infested with a highly virulent A2 *Pc* strain (code UEx1) isolated in
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46 185 Badajoz, Spain (Martín-García *et al.* 2015). Plants were inoculated at this time to
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48 186 coincide with maximum *Pc* inoculum in forest soils (Serrano *et al.* 2022). Inoculum was
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50 187 prepared following the procedure of Jung *et al.* (1996), mixing and twice autoclaving
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52 188 500 cm³ fine vermiculite, 40 cm³ whole oat grains and 350 ml multivitamin juice broth
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54 189 (200 mL/L juice, 800 mL/L demineralised water amended with 3 g/L CaCO₃) in 1L
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56 190 Erlenmeyer flasks. Individual pieces of *Pc* plugs were added to the Erlenmeyer flasks
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3 191 containing the medium and kept in an incubator for five weeks at 20 °C. When the
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5 192 inoculum was ready, it was rinsed with demineralised water to remove excess nutrients,
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7 193 and 12 ml inoculum was mixed with the first 3 cm of substrate in each individual cell,
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10 194 taking care not to damage seedling roots. After inoculation, trays were flooded for two
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12 195 days to promote sporangia production and zoospore release (Martínez-Arias *et al.*
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14 196 2022). Seedlings were then irrigated at field capacity once a week.
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19 198 In April 2017, when the second vegetative period started and 36% of the *Q. ilex* and
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21 199 14% of the *Q. suber* seedlings had died from *Pc* (Figure 2), plants were divided into two
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23 200 groups. The first group was irrigated at field capacity once a week ('absence of
24
25 201 drought') and the second group was irrigated at field capacity every three weeks
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27 202 ('presence of drought'). The drought treatment simulated a typical dry spring scenario,
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29 203 similar to the event occurring in Extremadura in spring and summer 2022, and lasted for
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31 204 five months. Each group of plants comprised 25 blocks.
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37 206 Soil moisture measurements taken on May 2017 using a Delta-Theta ML2X probe
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39 207 confirmed differences in soil water content between plants in the 'absence of drought'
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41 208 and 'presence of drought' treatments (0.182 ± 0.030 vs 0.039 ± 0.018 cm³cm⁻³,
42
43 209 respectively). To increase infection pressure by *Pc*, all seedlings were inoculated for a
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45 210 second time one month after the start of drought treatments (Figure 2) following the
46
47 211 same procedure as for the first inoculation. To confirm plant infection, *Pc* was
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49 212 successfully re-isolated in July 2017 from necrotic and non-necrotic fine roots in a
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51 213 subset of plant samples from each treatment (results not shown). We simulated
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53 214 environmental conditions similar to those experienced in the wild by oak plants after
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55 215 revegetation efforts; i.e., plant infection occurring in spring followed by summer
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3 216 drought (Corcobado *et al.* 2014; San-Eufrasio *et al.* 2021). The experiment lasted two
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5 217 years and ended in December 2017 (Figure 2).
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9 10 219 **Measurements and variables**

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12 220 Acorns were individually weighed and plant emergence was assessed weekly for four
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14 221 months. In June 2016, plant height was recorded in all seedlings. To determine whether
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16 222 drought affects the susceptibility of seedlings infected by *Pc* (objective 1), plant
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18 223 mortality was recorded weekly for 18 months after the first inoculation. Plant mortality
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20 224 was parameterised as 0 and 1, if the plant survived or not, and obtained for different
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22 225 time periods (Figure 2). Time to death of plants (life expectancy in days), a more
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24 226 explanatory variable than mortality because it is continuous and normally distributed,
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26 227 was also used for different time periods (Figure 2). When assessing seedling tolerance
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28 228 to stress, mortality is an appropriate parameter to obtain significances across
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30 229 treatments/populations/families if rates are 25 to 75%. However, if mortality rates are
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32 230 higher than 75%, time to death provides higher significances than mortality across
33
34 231 treatments/populations/families (Corcobado *et al.* 2017; Vivas *et al.* 2021). Eight
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36 232 variables, four for mortality and four for time to death, were used (Table 1): mortality a)
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38 233 after a single *Pc* inoculation (*mortality 1*), b) due to drought after a single *Pc*
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40 234 inoculation (*mortality 2_D*), c) of *Pc*-infected plants in the absence of drought from the
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42 235 beginning of the second vegetative period to peak mortality after the second inoculation
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44 236 with *Pc* (*mortality 3*), and d) of *Pc*-infected plants in the presence of drought from the
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46 237 beginning of the second vegetative period (start of drought treatment) to peak mortality
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48 238 after the second inoculation (*mortality 3_D*); and time to death of plants e) inoculated
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50 239 twice with *Pc* in the absence of drought and during the whole experiment (*time to death*
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52 240 *1*), f) inoculated twice with *Pc* in the presence of drought and during the whole
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241 experiment (*time to death* I_D), g) in the absence of drought from the beginning of the
 242 second vegetative period to the end of the experiment (*time to death* 2); and h) in the
 243 presence of drought from the beginning of the second vegetative period (start of drought
 244 treatment) to the end of the experiment (*time to death* 2_D) (see Figure 2).

245

246 **Statistical analyses**

247 To statistically assess the influence of drought on *Pc*-infected *Q. ilex* and *Q. suber*
 248 seedlings (objective 1), we used time to death of seedlings of the two species and
 249 scenarios (presence or absence of drought) from the second *Pc* inoculation to the end of
 250 the experiment. The following general linear mixed model was fitted:

251

$$252 \quad Y_{ijklm} = \mu + S_i + I_j + B(I)_{k(j)} + F(S)_{l(i)} + S \times I_{ij} + S \times B(I)_{ik(j)} + \varepsilon_{ijklm} \quad [1]$$

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254 where Y_{ijklm} is the time to death observation of the $ijklm^{\text{th}}$ seedling, μ is the overall mean,
 255 S_i is the fixed effect of the species i , I_j is the fixed effect of the drought scenario j , B_k is
 256 the fixed effect of the block k within the drought scenario j , $F(S)_{l(i)}$ is the random effect
 257 of the family l within species i , $S \times I_{ij}$ is the fixed interaction between species i and
 258 drought scenario j , $S \times B(I)_{ik(j)}$ is the fixed interaction between species i and block k
 259 within drought scenario j , and ε_{ijklm} is the random effect of the $ijklm^{\text{th}}$ seedling or error
 260 term. Because the dependent variable met the assumptions of normal distribution, the
 261 model was fitted using the SAS 9.4 MIXED procedure (SAS Institute, Cary, NC, USA;
 262 Littell *et al.* 2006), and variance components were estimated using the restricted
 263 maximum likelihood (REML) method. Significance of family within species random
 264 effect was tested using log-likelihood ratio tests by comparing the restricted log-
 265 likelihoods (RLL) of the full model with respective reduced models, excluding the

266 family effect (Yang, 2002). Degrees of freedom were calculated through the
 267 Satterthwaite approximation. Adjusted means for species, drought scenario, and species
 268 × drought scenario combinations were estimated using the LSMEANS statement of the
 269 MIXED procedure. Post-hoc comparisons among fixed effect levels were performed
 270 using the conservative Tukey-Kramer method.

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272 To quantify genetic variation in susceptibility to *Pc* in *Q. ilex* in the absence or presence
 273 of drought (objective 2) and assess the effect of the provenance sub-region, the
 274 following model was applied:

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$$276 \quad Y_{ijkl} = \mu + B_i + R_j + F(R)_{k(j)} + B \times R_{ij} + B \times F(R)_{ik(j)} + \varepsilon_{ijkl} \quad [2]$$

277

278 where Y_{ijkl} is the *mortality* or *time to death* observation of the $ijkl^{\text{th}}$ seedling, μ is the
 279 overall mean, B_i is the fixed effect of the block i , R_j is the fixed effect of the sub-region
 280 j , $F(R)_{k(j)}$ is the random effect of the family k within sub-region j , $B \times R_{ij}$ is the fixed
 281 interaction between block i and sub-region j , $B \times F(P)_{ik(j)}$ is the random interaction
 282 between block i and family k , and ε_{ijkl} is the random effect of the $ijkl^{\text{th}}$ seedling or error
 283 term. The corresponding fixed and random interactions with the block effect were
 284 dropped from the model for convergence purposes, as they showed no significance in
 285 preliminary analyses. Due to their low number, seedlings from the Montes de Toledo
 286 sub-region were excluded from the calculations.

287

288 For the mortality variables, generalised mixed models were fitted, and variance
 289 components and best linear unbiased predictors (BLUPS) of family effects (breeding
 290 values) were estimated using the restricted subject-specific pseudo likelihood (RSPL)

291 method of the GLIMMIX procedure in SAS, assuming a *binomial* probability distribution
 292 and a *logit* link function (Littell *et al.* 2006). For the normally distributed time to death
 293 variables, general mixed models were fitted using the MIXED procedure (Littell *et al.*
 294 2006). Variance components and family effects predicted by BLUP_s were estimated
 295 using the restricted maximum likelihood (REML) method. Significance of the family
 296 effect was tested using log-likelihood ratio tests by comparing the pseudo restricted log-
 297 likelihoods (PRLI for binary variables) or the restricted log-likelihoods (RLL for normal
 298 variables) of the full model with those of a reduced model, excluding the family effect
 299 (Yang, 2002). Degrees of freedom were calculated through the Satterthwaite
 300 approximation.

302 To obtain narrow sense individual heritability (h_i^2) in susceptibility to *Pc* for *Q. ilex* in
 303 the absence or presence of drought (objective 3), the variance components from the
 304 mixed models shown in Eq. 2 were used, but considering the sub-region as a random
 305 factor. h_i^2 was estimated as the ratio of additive genetic variance to total phenotypic
 306 variance. To correct the additive genetic variance estimates assuming average selfing
 307 rates of 1 to 3% (Ortego *et al.* 2010), a kinship coefficient (r) of 0.27 was used instead
 308 of the usual value of 0.25 for half-sibs. We calculated heritabilities for individual
 309 selection across all the sub-regions of Extremadura studied, following the formula
 310 described in Hamann *et al.* (2002):

$$311 \quad h_i^2 = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{r} \times \sigma_f^2\right) + \sigma_r^2}{\sigma_f^2 + \sigma_r^2 + \sigma_e^2}$$

312 where σ_f^2 is the family variance; σ_r^2 is the sub-region variance; r is the kinship
 313 coefficient; and σ_e^2 is the residual variance. For binary variables (Survival 1-4), an
 314 overdispersion term was added and residual variances were set at $\Pi^2/3$ (de Villemereuil

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3 315 *et al.* 2016). The standard error of heritability was estimated following the Delta method
4
5 316 based on asymptotic estimates of the variances and covariances of the variance
6
7 317 components of the mixed models (Lynch and Walsh 1998).
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12 319 Genetic (family-level) correlations between mortality, time to death, seed weight, time
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14 320 to emerge and plant height variables and associated standard errors were estimated
15
16 321 using a mixed bivariate repeated measures analysis on the model shown in Eq. 2
17
18 322 (Holland 2006).
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24 324 **Results**

26 325 **Differences in susceptibility among species and infection scenarios**

28 326 Mortality was heterogeneously distributed throughout the experiment and was highest
29
30 327 one month after *Pc* inoculation and one month after the beginning of water deprivation
31
32 328 (Figure 2). Ten months after a single *Pc*-inoculation, cumulated mortalities were 36 and
33
34 329 14% in *Q. ilex* and *Q. suber* plants, respectively (*mortality 1*, Figure 2). Water
35
36 330 deprivation induced further plant mortality, which was higher in *Q. suber* than in *Q. ilex*
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38 331 (55 vs 15%, respectively; *mortality 2_D*, Figure 2). However, under regular watering, no
39
40 332 further mortality was observed in either species (*mortality 2*, Figure 2). Mortality ceased
41
42 333 when plants were flooded at the second *Pc* inoculation, and restarted one month later,
43
44 334 causing in a single week mortalities of 63 and 55% (*Q. ilex*) and 27 and 31% (*Q. suber*)
45
46 335 in the absence or presence of drought, respectively. At the end of the experiment,
47
48 336 cumulative mortality was ~97% in *Q. ilex* seedlings irrespective of the drought scenario,
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50 337 and 59 and 96% in *Q. suber* seedlings in the absence or presence of drought,
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52 338 respectively (Figure 2).
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3 340 Time to death of seedlings after the second *Pc* inoculation was significantly influenced
4
5 341 by species, drought scenario and their interaction ($P < 0.001$; Table 2). The within-
6
7 342 population family effect was also highly significant ($\chi^2 < 0.001$), indicating individual
8
9 343 tree genetic variation. In the second growing season, mean life expectancy of seedlings
10
11 344 was significantly higher in *Q. suber* than in *Q. ilex*, at 99 and 43 days, respectively
12
13 345 (Figure 3a). In the absence or presence of drought, life expectancy of double inoculated
14
15 346 seedlings was 86 and 56 days, respectively (Figure 3b). The effect of drought stress on
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17 347 plant life expectancy was observed only in *Q. suber* (Figure 3c), as indicated by the
18
19 348 significant species \times drought interaction (Table 2).
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25
26 350 BLUP_s obtained from the general and generalised models following Eq. 2 for *mortality 1*
27
28 351 and *time to death 2* variables (absence of drought) were lowest and highest for *Q. suber*
29
30 352 families, respectively, indicating a high level of tolerance to *Pc* in this species (Figure
31
32 353 4a, c). In contrast, when inoculated seedlings were subjected to *Pc* and drought, most *Q.*
33
34 354 *suber* families showed the highest BLUP for *mortality 2_D* and the lowest BLUP for *time to*
35
36 355 *death 2_D*, indicating a low level of tolerance to drought stress after *Pc* infection in this
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38 356 species (Figure 4b, d).
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43 358 **Geographic and additive genetic variation and heritabilities of tolerance in *Q. ilex***

44
45 359 Results from the general and generalised mixed models following Eq. 2 showed a
46
47 360 significant ($P < 0.05$) *Q. ilex* sub-region effect only for *mortality 3_D* (Table 3). This
48
49 361 effect is attributable to the higher mortality of *Pc*-inoculated seedlings from the Tiétar-
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51 362 Norte del Tajo sub-region in the presence of drought compared to seedlings from the
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53 363 other three sub-regions (Figure 5).
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3 365 The family effect was significant for all variables. Associated individual narrow sense
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5 366 heritabilities ranged from 0.06 to 0.63 (Table 3). Heritability was highest for plant
6
7 367 mortality after a single inoculation in the absence of drought (0.63 ± 0.12 for *mortality 1*
8
9 368 after 36% mortality; Figure 2) and lowest for time to death in seedlings inoculated twice
10
11 369 in the presence of drought (0.06 ± 0.04 for *time to death 2* after 96% mortality; Figure
12
13 370 2; Table 3). The results showed that genetic control patterns of seedling governing
14
15 371 tolerance to *Pc* changed over time, probably depending on the selection pressure by the
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17 372 pathogen (highest h_i^2 values for single inoculation) and the number of stressors (lowest
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19 373 h_i^2 values for combined stress).
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26 375 **Genetic correlations between variables and selection of most tolerant *Q. ilex*** 27 28 376 **families**

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30 377 Family-level (genetic) correlations were highly significant between variables similar in
31
32 378 type (within *mortality* or *time to death*) and period (starting and ending at the same
33
34 379 time; Table 4). Thus *mortality 3* and *mortality 3_D* (Figure 6a), *time to death 1* and *time*
35
36 380 *to death 1_D* (Figure 6b), and *time to death 2* and *time to death 2_D* (Figure 6c) correlated
37
38 381 significantly and positively, showing consistency in tolerance in response to *Pc* between
39
40 382 family rankings irrespective of drought stress. However, the rankings of mortality
41
42 383 (Figure S1a) and time to death (Figure S1b) of some families altered slightly depending
43
44 384 on water availability. Time to death was strongly dependent on seed weight and plant
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46 385 height ($p < 0.001$) and was not affected by time to emerge (Table S2).
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52 53 387 **Discussion**

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55 388 Negative interactive effects in *Q. ilex* and *Q. suber* forests are likely to occur much
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57 389 more often and with greater impact under projected future climate conditions (Duque-
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3 390 Lazo *et al.* 2016; Moral *et al.* 2023) and the continuous emergence of plant pathogens,
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5 391 including those belonging to the genus *Phytophthora* (Mora-Sala *et al.* 2019; Dorado *et*
6
7 392 *al.* 2023). In this work, the genetic basis of tolerance to *Pc* was determined by
8
9 393 challenging 66 *Q. ilex* progenies in the absence or presence of severe drought during
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11 394 two vegetative periods. The use of nine additional progenies of *Q. suber* as controls
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13 395 revealed four important findings, as discussed in the following subsections.
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19 397 **Differences in susceptibility to *Pc* between *Q. ilex* and *Q. suber* disappear in the**
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21 398 **presence of severe drought**
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24 399 We provide further evidence of *Q. ilex* oak as a more susceptible species than *Q. suber*
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26 400 to *Pc* under regular watering, as reported in the literature (Robin *et al.* 1998, 2001;
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28 401 Camilo-Alves *et al.* 2013; León *et al.* 2017). Previous studies reported drought as a
29
30 402 predisposing factor that enhances the susceptibility of *Q. ilex* to *Pc* (Corcobado *et al.*
31
32 403 2014). Here we report *Pc* as a predisposing factor that also enhances susceptibility to
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34 404 drought in *Q. suber*. When infected trees were subjected to water deprivation in spring,
35
36 405 early summer mortality of *Q. ilex* and *Q. suber* was 10 and 218% higher, respectively,
37
38 406 than in trees under regular watering (Figure 2). Evidence of this synergistic effect was
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40 407 reported at the physiological and proteomic level in *Q. ilex* (San-Eufrasio *et al.* 2021),
41
42 408 but not in *Q. suber*. According to our results, the synergistic effect of both stresses was
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44 409 greater in *Q. suber* than in *Q. ilex*, confirming the first hypothesis of our study. Our
45
46 410 results seem counterintuitive, because if *Pc* causes more damage to the *Q. ilex* than the
47
48 411 *Q. suber* root system (Robin *et al.* 2001; León *et al.* 2017), it could be inferred that the
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50 412 species more susceptible to *Pc* will be more vulnerable to subsequent drought (Maurel
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52 413 *et al.* 2001).
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3 415 The lack of correlation between *mortality* 1 and *mortality* 2_D could be interpreted as a
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5 416 lack of a relation between responses to *Pc* and drought within *Q. ilex* families. This
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7 417 agrees with the different physiological responses observed in response to *Pc* infection
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9 418 and water stress in *Q. ilex* seedlings (Ruiz Gómez *et al.* 2018). Different strategies of
10
11 419 oaks in response to *Pc* may explain the different behaviour of our two species to
12
13 420 drought stress. *Phytophthora cinnamomi* infection in *Q. ilex* decreases photosynthesis
14
15 421 and growth and increases stomatal closure and leaf mass fraction (Maurel *et al.* 2001;
16
17 422 Ruiz-Gómez *et al.* 2018; López-Sánchez *et al.* 2022), probably counteracting the effect
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19 423 of root loss. *Quercus ilex* root loss caused by *Pc* is so severe that the soil water content
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21 424 in the rhizosphere does not decrease (Robin *et al.* 2001; Corcobado *et al.* 2013),
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23 425 mitigating the effect of drought and helping plants to survive longer. *Quercus ilex* does
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25 426 not immediately replace damaged fine roots (León *et al.* 2017), avoiding rapid
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27 427 carbohydrate depletion. On the contrary, some proteins associated with starch
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29 428 biosynthesis showed an increase on inoculation (Sghaier-Hammami *et al.* 2013). This
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31 429 conservative strategy probably allows *Q. ilex* to cope with further stress. In *Q. suber*,
32
33 430 however, *Pc* infection involves a reduction in photosynthetic rates (Luque *et al.* 1999;
34
35 431 Homet *et al.* 2019) and rapid fine root replacement (León *et al.* 2017). Carbon
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37 432 starvation can occur in *Q. suber* if carbon supply by photosynthesis and mobilisation is
38
39 433 lower than the metabolic carbon demand for root investment. *Quercus ilex* is therefore
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41 434 probably more predisposed than *Q. suber* to drought stress. Root damage and changes in
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43 435 carbohydrate balance in plants were not assessed here, in part because they require
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45 436 destructive methods, but these factors may have shed further light on the results.
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49 438 Our results showed that the less susceptible *Q. suber*, in the absence of drought, can
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51 439 counteract the negative effects of *Pc* (León *et al.* 2017; Homet *et al.* 2019). However,
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3 440 when infected trees were further subjected to drought during summer, final mortalities
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5 441 in *Q. ilex* and *Q. suber* were similar (97 and 96%, respectively; Figure 2). The negative
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7 442 effects of drought on the development of *Pc* in soil (Serrano *et al.* 2022; Homet *et al.*
8
9 443 2023) or bark (Luque *et al.* 2000) were not assessed here, but given the high plant
10
11 444 mortality observed, these effects were probably negligible. The results indicate that
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13 445 under climate change scenarios of drought predicted for the south of the Iberia
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15 446 Peninsula (Moral *et al.* 2023), *Q. suber* forests are likely to be as vulnerable as *Q. ilex*
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17 447 forests to *Pc*.
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21 448

22 23 24 449 **Evidence of geographic variation in susceptibility of *Q. ilex* to combined *Pc* and** 25 26 450 **drought**

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28 451 No differences in susceptibility to *Pc* were observed among provenance sub-regions of
29
30 452 *Q. ilex* in Extremadura, probably because of the small size of the study area and lack of
31
32 453 adaptation of holm oak to the pathogen, or because phenotypic plasticity in *Q. ilex*
33
34 454 prevails over local adaptation (Gimeno *et al.* 2009). However, we found variation in
35
36 455 susceptibility to *Pc* among sub-regions in the presence of drought (sub-region was
37
38 456 significant for *mortality* 3_D ; Table 3), indicating geographic variation in susceptibility to
39
40 457 combined stress in the Extremadurese provenance region. Families from the northern
41
42 458 region had the highest mortality, probably because they are less well adapted to drought
43
44 459 stress. This result partially confirms our second hypothesis, as no genetic variation
45
46 460 across sub-regions was observed when infected plants received regular watering
47
48 461 treatment. **Intraspecific variation in *Q. ilex* across its circum-Mediterranean distribution**
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51
52 462 **has been documented for drought tolerance (Nardini *et al.* 2000; Gimeno *et al.* 2009;**
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54 463 **Navarro-Cerrillo *et al.* 2018; San-Eufrasio *et al.* 2020), and the high heterozygosity,**
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56 464 **allelic richness, spatial differentiation and genetic diversity in tolerance to herbivory of**
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3 465 *Q. ilex* (Guzmán *et al.* 2015; Solla *et al.* 2016; Fernández i Marti *et al.* 2018) supports a
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5 466 significant geographic variation in susceptibility to combined *Pc* and drought.
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7 467 Moreover, our results agree with a recent study reporting geographic variability in
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9 468 mortality of *Q. ilex* due to combined *Pc* and drought (San-Eufrasio *et al.* 2021).
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14 470 **Susceptibility of *Q. ilex* in response to combined *Pc* infection and drought is**
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16 471 **heritable, allowing tree genetic improvement**

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19 472 Our study reports significant additive genetic variation in the susceptibility of *Q. ilex* to
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21 473 *Pc* infection, providing scientific support for a genetic improvement programme to
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23 474 reduce the susceptibility of *Q. ilex* to decline. The programme started in 2020, based on
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25 475 an integrated, collaborative, cross-institutional species restoration plan supported by the
26
27 476 Spanish Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge (Pérez *et al.*
28
29 477 2020; Martínez *et al.* 2023). The results obtained here show significant genetic control
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31 478 in two variables associated with susceptibility to decline (mortality and time to death),
32
33 479 confirming the hypothesis that significant intraspecific variation in susceptibility to *Pc*
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35 480 at individual level occurs in *Q. ilex* in the absence or presence of drought and
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37 481 supporting the possibility of selecting for increased tolerance.
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44 483 Family variance component estimates of time to death in *Q. ilex* were highest in the
45
46 484 presence of drought (Table 3). Because *time to death* I_D is highly heritable, involves the
47
48 485 two most common stressors in dehesas, and has a highly significant correlation with
49
50 486 *time to death* I , this variable could be used to select the most tolerant *Q. ilex* families.
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52 487 Using a selection intensity of 20%, *time to death* I_D would provide the 13 mother trees
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54 488 most tolerant to combined stress (Figure 7). As far as we know, this study is the first to
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3 489 provide quantitative estimations of heritability in *Q. ilex* in response to *Pc* infection and
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5 490 define a breeding population against combined stress in oak.
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10 492 **Genetic control of susceptibility in *Q. ilex* changes over time as a function of stress**

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12 493 The variables analysed showed that genetic control of the response of *Q. ilex* to *Pc*
13
14 494 changed over time as a function of stress. *Mortality 1* assessed plant response during the
15
16 495 first growing season after *Pc* inoculation, while *mortalities 3* and *3_D* assessed plant
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18 496 response during the second growing season to two different, more severe, conditions
19
20 497 imposed by a second inoculation in the absence or presence of drought (Figure 2).
21
22 498 Heritability estimates, high for *mortality 1* and lower for *mortalities 3* and *3_D* (Table 3),
23
24 499 provide evidence of changing patterns of genetic control in the susceptibility of *Q. ilex*
25
26 500 to *Pc* over time as a function of stress. While *Q. ilex* families showed significant genetic
27
28 501 patterns in response to *Pc* at mortality rates of 36%, additional stress during the second
29
30 502 growing season, as indicated by further mortality, probably exceeded the threshold of
31
32 503 the species for showing genetic differences in response to *Pc*. The high heritability
33
34 504 estimates observed during the first growing season could be explained by the significant
35
36 505 effect of seed weight and plant height on plant mortality (maternal effects; Table S2).
37
38 506 These genetically controlled variables are highly dependent on the mother tree (Solla *et*
39
40 507 *al.* 2016; Corcobado *et al.* 2017; Vivas *et al.* 2021), and their effect decreases over time.
41
42 508 Additional evidence of changing patterns of genetic control of *Q. ilex* susceptibility to
43
44 509 *Pc* over time as a function of stress is provided by the non-significant genetic
45
46 510 correlations among variables assessed in different seasons, e.g., *mortalities 1 vs 3* and
47
48 511 *time to death 1 vs 2* (Table 4). The genetic response of *Salix viminalis* to the gall midge
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50 512 *Dasineura marginemtorquens*, and of *Picea mariana* to the sawfly *Pikonema*
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3 513 *alaskensis*, assessed through heritability estimates, also changed over time when the
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5 514 infestation increased (Strong *et al.* 1993; Leinekugel le Cocq *et al.* 2005).
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10 516 For breeding purposes, plants should be challenged with the appropriate stress level to
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12 517 allow maximum genetic differentiation and appropriate selection. Significant genetic
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14 518 correlations among variables during the second growing season in the absence or
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16
17 519 presence of drought (Figure 5) provide evidence that robust selection of families
18
19 520 tolerant to *Pc* is possible, irrespective of drought stress. Robustness of selection should
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21 521 be further explored in *Q. suber*, given the significant *Pc* × drought interaction observed
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23 522 here (Figure 3c).
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28 524 **Conclusion**

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31 525 In the absence of effective methods to control *Phytophthora* disease in Mediterranean
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33 526 forests, breeding for tolerance to combined *Pc* infection and drought is the best long-
34
35 527 term solution to protect oaks at risk of decline. Our results provide evidence of
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37 528 significant additive genetic variation to combined stress in *Q. ilex*, indicating that
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39 529 screening for tolerance is possible. The study confirmed two hypotheses. Firstly,
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41 530 drought stress induces early mortality of *Pc*-infected oak seedlings, much more in *Q.*
42
43 531 *suber* than in *Q. ilex*. In the absence of drought, *Q. ilex* is the more susceptible species
44
45 532 to *Pc*, but in the presence of drought after *Pc* infection, *Q. suber* is as susceptible as *Q.*
46
47 533 *ilex*. Secondly, significant intraspecific variation in susceptibility to *Pc* at individual
48
49 534 level occurs in *Q. ilex*, both in the absence and the presence of drought. Whereas inter-
50
51 535 family variation in time to death in *Q. ilex* was highest in the presence of drought,
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53 536 genetic control of susceptibility in *Q. ilex* decreased over time as plant stress increased.
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4

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18
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20

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22
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24
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28
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42
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51 559 **Data availability**
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53 560 The data used in this article will be shared following reasonable request to the
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55 561 corresponding author.
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787 **Table 1.** Description of the variables used, corresponding to different time periods of
 788 infection, drought scenarios and time points of maximum mortality (see Figure 2).

Variable	Distribution	# seedlings	Description
<i>Mortality 1</i>	Binomial (1/0)	5,625	Seedling mortality after single inoculation with <i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i> (<i>Pc</i>) in absence of drought from 15 June 2016 (first inoculation) to 20 April 2017
<i>Mortality 2_D</i>	Binomial (1/0)	1,638	Seedling mortality after single <i>Pc</i> inoculation in presence of drought from 20 April 2017 (beginning of drought) to 19 May 2017 (second <i>Pc</i> inoculation)
<i>Mortality 3</i>	Binomial (1/0)	1,984	Mortality of <i>Pc</i> -inoculated seedlings in absence of drought, from 20 April 2017 (beginning of vegetative period) to 17 June 2017, when a mortality peak occurred
<i>Mortality 3_D</i>	Binomial (1/0)	1,638	Mortality of <i>Pc</i> -inoculated seedlings subjected to drought from 20 April 2017 (beginning of vegetative period, when drought started) to 17 June 2017, when a mortality peak occurred
<i>Time to death 1</i>	Normal	3,040	Days to death of seedlings inoculated twice with <i>Pc</i> in absence of drought from 15 June 2016 (first <i>Pc</i> inoculation) to 27 December 2017 (end of experiment)
<i>Time to death 1_D</i>	Normal	2,585	Days to death of seedlings inoculated twice with <i>Pc</i> in presence of drought from 15 June 2016 (first <i>Pc</i> inoculation) to 27 December 2017 (end of experiment)
<i>Time to death 2</i>	Normal	1,984	Days to death of <i>Pc</i> -inoculated seedlings in absence of drought from 20 April 2017 (beginning of vegetative period) to 27 December 2017 (end of experiment)
<i>Time to death 2_D</i>	Normal	1,638	Days to death of <i>Pc</i> -inoculated seedlings in presence of drought from 20 April 2017 (beginning of vegetative period, when drought started) to 27 December 2017 (end of experiment)

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3 790 **Table 2.** Summary of the linear mixed model analysis [Eq. 1] for *time to death* of
4
5 791 *Quercus ilex* and *Q. suber* seedlings after two inoculations with *Phytophthora*
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7 792 *cinnamomi* in absence or presence of drought (scenario). For the species, drought
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9 793 scenario and block (nested within drought scenario) fixed effects and their interactions,
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11 794 degrees of freedom, *F*-ratio and associated significance level (***; $P < 0.001$) are
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13 795 shown. For family and residual random effects, variance component estimates \pm
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15 796 standard errors (VC \pm s.e.), corresponding variance percentage (%) and associated
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17 797 significance level (***; $\chi^2 < 0.001$) are shown.

Fixed effects	DF (NumDF, DenDF)	<i>F</i> -ratio	$P > F$
Species	1, 76.9	73.13	<0.001 ***
Drought scenario	1, 3693.0	124.00	<0.001 ***
Block (drought scenario)	48, 3653.0	2.57	<0.001 ***
Species \times drought scenario	1, 3693.0	119.84	<0.001 ***
Species \times block (drought scenario)	48, 3653.0	2.24	<0.001 ***
Random effects	VC \pm s.e.	%	$P > \chi^2$
Family (species)	273.6 \pm 54.2	12	<0.001 ***
Residual	2016.5 \pm 47.3	-	-

799 **Table 3.** Results of the linear mixed model analyses [Eq. 2] for the four *mortality* and four *time to death* variables assessed in *Q. ilex*, and narrow
 800 sense individual heritabilities (h_i^2) and associated standard errors. For the sub-region and block fixed effects, *F*-ratios and associated significance
 801 levels are shown; for family (nested within sub-region) and residual random effects, variance component estimates \pm standard errors (VC \pm s.e.)
 802 and associated significance levels (ns, $\chi^2 > 0.05$; *, $\chi^2 < 0.05$; **, $\chi^2 < 0.01$; ***, $\chi^2 < 0.001$) are shown.

Source of variation / Trait						
Fixed effects	Sub-region <i>F</i> -ratio		Sub-region NumDF, DenDF	Block <i>F</i> -ratio		Block NumDF, DenDF
<i>Mortality 1</i>	0.27	$p = 0.845$ ns	3, 68.9	2.86	$p < 0.001$ ***	49, 5480
<i>Mortality 2_D</i>	0.68	$p = 0.569$ ns	3, 63.1	1.41	$p = 0.091$ ns	23, 1586
<i>Mortality 3</i>	2.37	$p = 0.077$ ns	3, 70.0	3.76	$p < 0.001$ ***	25, 1925
<i>Mortality 3_D</i>	3.75	$p = 0.016$ *	3, 51.7	3.66	$p < 0.001$ ***	23, 1585
<i>Time to death 1</i>	0.23	$p = 0.877$ ns	3, 61.2	3.64	$p < 0.001$ ***	25, 2902
<i>Time to death 1_D</i>	0.03	$p = 0.992$ ns	3, 60.0	2.09	$p = 0.002$ **	23, 2463
<i>Time to death 2</i>	1.26	$p = 0.297$ ns	3, 58.0	1.54	$p = 0.042$ *	25, 1894
<i>Time to death 2_D</i>	2.36	$p = 0.082$ ns	3, 51.0	4.70	$p < 0.001$ ***	23, 1552
Random effects	Family (sub-region) VC \pm s.e.		Residual VC \pm s.e.	$h_i^2 \pm$ s.e.		
<i>Mortality 1</i>	0.702 \pm 0.144	*** (1)	-	0.63 \pm 0.12		
<i>Mortality 2_D</i>	0.215 \pm 0.102	***	-	0.21 \pm 0.10		
<i>Mortality 3</i>	0.121 \pm 0.050	***	-	0.12 \pm 0.06		
<i>Mortality 3_D</i>	0.093 \pm 0.056	*	-	0.14 \pm 0.05		
<i>Time to death 1</i>	2849.810 \pm 593.570	***	19246.0 \pm 501.2	0.45 \pm 0.07		
<i>Time to death 1_D</i>	3336.370 \pm 726.140	***	23094.0 \pm 653.5	0.44 \pm 0.07		
<i>Time to death 2</i>	24.286 \pm 14.625	*	1661.3 \pm 54.0	0.06 \pm 0.04		
<i>Time to death 2_D</i>	50.757 \pm 22.197	***	1614.4 \pm 58.0	0.14 \pm 0.06		

803

804

805 **Table 4.** REML estimates of genetic correlation coefficients ($r_g \pm$ s.e.) between pairs of variables described in Table 2 for *Quercus ilex* families.
 806 Associated significance levels of the log-likelihood ratio tests (ns, $P > 0.05$; *, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$; ***, $P < 0.001$) of each genetic correlation
 807 are shown. Significant genetic correlations ($\chi^2 < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

	<i>Mortality</i> 2 _D	<i>Mortality</i> 3	<i>Mortality</i> 3 _D	<i>Time to death</i> 1	<i>Time to death</i> 1 _D	<i>Time to death</i> 2	<i>Time to death</i> 2 _D
<i>Mortality</i> 1	0.01 ± 0.24	-0.15 ± 0.23	0.14 ± 0.25	-0.98*** ± 0.01	-0.99*** ± 0.01	0.50* ± 0.23	0.18 ± 0.22
<i>Mortality</i> 2 _D	-	0.22 ± 0.32	0.35 ± 0.31	-0.11 ± 0.25	-0.11 ± 0.23	-0.23 ± 0.36	-0.51* ± 0.24
<i>Mortality</i> 3	-	-	0.83** ± 0.27	-0.36 ± 0.22	-0.08 ± 0.23	-0.92*** ± 0.19	-1.07*** ± 0.23
<i>Mortality</i> 3 _D	-	-	-	-0.29 ± 0.25	-0.55* ± 0.19	-0.73* ± 0.34	-0.83* ± 0.15
<i>Time to death</i> 1	-	-	-	-	0.99*** ± 0.01	0.46 ± 0.22	0.08 ± 0.24
<i>Time to death</i> 1 _D	-	-	-	-	-	-0.16 ± 0.26	0.43 ± 0.20
<i>Time to death</i> 2	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.94** ± 0.30

809

810 **Figure 1.** Distribution of *Quercus ilex* (green) and *Q. suber* (orange) in Extremadura,
 811 Spain, according to Junta de Extremadura (2020), and location of the 75 mother trees
 812 (circles) where acorns were collected. Extremadura has one provenance region of forest
 813 reproductive material for *Q. ilex* (Extremadurensis, coded 11), divided into five sub-
 814 regions grouping ecologically similar areas: Tiétar-Norte del Tajo (11a), Sierra de San
 815 Pedro-Guadalupe (11b), Montes de Toledo (11c), Tierra de Barros-La Serena (11d) and
 816 Sierra Morena Occidental (11e; Jiménez *et al.* 1996).

817

818 **Figure 2.** Mortality of *Quercus ilex* (a) and *Q. suber* (b) seedlings after first inoculation
 819 with *Phytophthora cinnamomi* (*Pc*) in June 2016 in the absence of drought (black dots),
 820 with severe drought treatment on 20 April 2017 in half the experimental blocks (red
 821 dots), and second *Pc* inoculation in May 2017 in all seedlings. No plant mortality was
 822 observed from September 2016 to April 2017 and September 2017 to December 2017.
 823 Variables used to assess genetic variability of susceptibility in *Q. ilex* are described in
 824 Table 1 and indicated in italics in (a).

825

826 **Figure 3.** Time to death of *Quercus ilex* and *Q. suber* seedlings after second inoculation
 827 with *Phytophthora cinnamomi*, and effect of species (a), drought (absent vs present; b)
 828 and species × drought (c). Bars are LSMMeans ± s.e. and different letters indicate
 829 significant differences ($P < 0.05$) using the Tukey-Kramer method.

830

831 **Figure 4.** Best linear unbiased predictors (BLUP or breeding values \pm s.e.) of mortality 1
 832 (a), mortality 2_D (b), time to death 2 (c) and time to death 2_D (d) of seedlings from 66
 833 *Quercus ilex* (green bars) and the nine *Q. suber* (orange bars) half-sib families. See
 834 Table 1 for a description of the variables. Family codes are shown in the *x*-axis.

835

836 **Figure 5.** Mortality of *Quercus ilex* seedlings from provenance sub-regions in
837 Extremadura, Spain, after inoculation with *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in presence of
838 drought. Location of sub-regions is shown in Figure 1. Bars are LSMeans \pm s.e. and
839 different letters indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$) using the Tukey-Kramer
840 method.

841

842 **Figure 6.** Genetic correlations between mortality (a), and time to death (b, c) of 66
 843 *Quercus ilex* families inoculated with *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in the absence
 844 (*mortality 3*, *time to death 1*, and *time to death 2* variables) or presence (*mortality 3_D*,
 845 *time to death 1_D*, and *time to death 2_D* variables) of drought. See Table 1 for a
 846 description of the variables. Data points represent best linear unbiased predictors
 847 (BLUPS) for families. Regression lines, bivariate genetic correlation coefficients (r_g),
 848 significance levels (**, $P < 0.01$; ***, $P < 0.001$) and standard errors are shown.

849

850

851 **Figure 7.** Time to death of seedlings from 66 *Quercus ilex* half-sib families inoculated
 852 with *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in the presence of drought. A selection intensity of 20%
 853 would include the 13 most tolerant *Q. ilex* mother trees (dark green).

For Review Only

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Table S1. Location and climate characteristics of the 66 *Quercus ilex* and 9 *Q. suber* mother trees sampled. Climate data corresponds to the normal series for 1961-1990 and was generated with the ClimateEU v4.63 software package (Marchi et al. 2020). This software locally downscales historical climate data layers into scale-free point estimates of climate values.

Species	Provenance region or sub-region ¹	Family	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation (m)	MAT (°C) ¹	MWMT (°C) ²	MCM T (°C) ³	MAP (mm) ⁴	MSP (mm) ⁵	SHM ⁶
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11d	1	38.4990	-7.2165	250	16.5	25.0	9.2	544	93	268.8
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11d	2	38.5004	-7.2170	250	16.5	25.0	9.2	544	93	268.7
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11d	3	38.5011	-7.2105	250	16.5	25.0	9.2	544	93	268.5
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	4	38.1315	-6.2879	850	14.0	24.2	5.7	662	108	223.4
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11d	5	38.4253	-6.5404	550	15.2	24.7	7.3	618	107	230.2
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11d	6	38.4251	-6.5389	550	15.2	24.7	7.3	620	107	229.8
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	7	38.3201	-7.0942	250	16.5	25.0	9.1	546	90	278.1
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	8	38.3202	-7.0947	250	16.5	25.0	9.1	546	90	278.2
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	9	38.3189	-7.0971	250	16.5	25.0	9.1	545	90	279.0
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	10	38.1001	-6.3982	850	14.0	23.9	5.8	662	107	222.9
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	11	38.0974	-6.4157	850	13.9	23.8	5.8	677	110	216.0
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	12	38.0975	-6.4161	850	13.9	23.8	5.8	677	110	216.0
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	13	38.2095	-6.8918	350	16.2	25.1	8.6	550	89	281.7
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	14	38.2082	-6.8962	350	16.2	25.1	8.6	549	89	282.0
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	15	38.2087	-6.8979	350	16.2	25.1	8.6	547	89	282.8
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	16	37.9829	-6.2083	850	14.2	24.7	5.6	623	95	259.0
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	17	37.9824	-6.2074	850	14.2	24.7	5.6	623	95	258.9
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	18	37.9831	-6.2074	850	14.2	24.7	5.6	623	95	258.7
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	25	39.0794	-6.0768	250	16.7	26.6	8.2	485	94	281.5
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	26	38.1705	-5.8955	850	14.2	24.9	5.4	646	105	236.8
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	27	38.1706	-5.8959	850	14.2	24.9	5.4	646	105	236.7
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	28	38.1705	-5.8965	850	14.2	24.9	5.4	646	105	236.4
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11c	29	38.9119	-5.0026	550	15.3	26.0	6.3	522	111	234.3
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11d	30	38.8039	-5.9907	500	15.6	25.9	7.0	531	99	262.2
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11d	31	38.8045	-5.9908	500	15.6	25.9	7.0	532	99	262.0
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11d	32	38.8082	-5.9971	500	15.6	26.0	7.0	531	99	263.3
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11d	33	38.7113	-5.5864	550	15.5	26.2	6.6	534	98	267.4
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11d	34	38.5554	-5.4227	550	15.5	26.3	6.7	577	104	253.5
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11d	35	38.5554	-5.4223	550	15.5	26.3	6.7	576	104	253.6
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11d	36	38.5554	-5.4225	550	15.5	26.3	6.7	576	104	253.5
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11a	37	40.0129	-6.7808	450	15.1	24.6	7.1	630	124	199.1
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11a	38	40.0128	-6.7805	450	15.1	24.6	7.1	630	123	199.2
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11a	39	40.0130	-6.7805	450	15.1	24.6	7.1	630	124	199.2
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11a	40	40.0883	-6.7341	450	15.0	24.5	7.0	619	123	199.4
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11a	41	40.2185	-6.2664	550	14.3	24.1	6.1	522	118	203.6
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	42	39.5537	-6.6455	550	15.1	25.0	7.0	579	114	219.3
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	43	39.5549	-6.6442	550	15.1	25.0	7.0	579	114	219.1
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	44	39.5546	-6.6446	550	15.1	25.0	7.0	579	114	219.2
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	45	39.7959	-6.3142	450	15.4	25.3	7.1	517	110	229.8
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	46	39.7934	-6.3136	450	15.4	25.3	7.1	514	110	231.0

Species	Provenance region or sub-region ¹	Family	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation (m)	MAT (°C) ²	MWMT (°C) ³	MCMT (°C) ⁴	MAP (mm) ⁵	MSP (mm) ⁶	SHM ⁷
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11a	47	40.2462	-5.9557	450	14.7	24.4	6.4	462	116	210.3
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11a	48	40.2476	-5.9527	450	14.7	24.4	6.4	463	117	208.9
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11a	49	40.2489	-5.9592	450	14.7	24.4	6.4	457	115	212.3
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	50	39.7178	-5.9858	400	15.6	25.7	7.2	467	105	244.4
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	51	39.7179	-5.9863	400	15.6	25.7	7.2	467	105	244.6
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	52	39.7189	-5.9884	400	15.6	25.7	7.2	466	105	245.2
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	53	39.4268	-5.2850	550	14.9	25.4	6.2	468	112	226.3
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	55	39.4265	-5.2856	550	14.9	25.4	6.2	469	112	226.1
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	56	39.2621	-5.1735	550	15.2	26.1	6.1	440	98	265.0
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	57	39.2628	-5.1730	550	15.2	26.1	6.1	440	98	265.1
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	58	39.3125	-5.1217	550	15.1	26.0	6.1	440	102	255.8
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	59	39.3133	-5.1235	550	15.1	26.0	6.1	439	101	256.6
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	60	39.3125	-5.1235	550	15.1	26.1	6.1	439	101	257.7
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	61	39.2915	-5.0766	550	15.1	26.0	6.0	443	102	254.0
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	62	39.2909	-5.0771	550	15.1	26.0	6.0	443	102	254.0
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	63	39.2914	-5.0776	550	15.1	26.0	6.0	443	102	253.8
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	64	39.1350	-5.6760	350	16.2	26.7	7.5	466	95	281.4
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	65	39.1349	-5.6754	350	16.2	26.7	7.5	466	95	281.2
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	66	39.1371	-5.6768	350	16.2	26.7	7.5	465	95	281.6
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11a	69	40.2393	-6.0580	400	15.0	24.6	6.7	464	112	220.1
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11a	70	40.2400	-6.0596	400	15.0	24.6	6.7	464	112	219.9
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11a	71	40.2398	-6.0617	400	15.0	24.6	6.7	465	112	219.7
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11b	72	39.0769	-6.0767	250	16.7	26.6	8.2	485	94	281.9
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11d	73	38.7108	-5.5869	550	15.5	26.2	6.6	535	98	267.4
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11e	74	38.1312	-6.2875	850	14.0	24.2	5.7	663	108	223.3
<i>Q. ilex</i>	11d	75	38.7104	-5.5866	550	15.5	26.2	6.6	535	98	267.4
<i>Q. suber</i>	5	19	37.9980	-6.2978	850	14.1	24.4	5.7	643	101	241.7
<i>Q. suber</i>	5	20	37.9966	-6.2975	850	14.1	24.4	5.7	642	101	241.8
<i>Q. suber</i>	5	21	37.9975	-6.2973	850	14.1	24.4	5.7	642	101	241.6
<i>Q. suber</i>	2	22	39.0447	-6.2578	300	16.4	26.2	8.1	513	99	264.6
<i>Q. suber</i>	2	23	39.0420	-6.1486	300	16.5	26.3	8.0	506	98	268.7
<i>Q. suber</i>	2	24	39.0421	-6.1501	300	16.5	26.3	8.0	506	98	268.9
<i>Q. suber</i>	3	54	39.4271	-5.2852	550	14.9	25.4	6.2	468	112	226.4
<i>Q. suber</i>	3	67	39.4157	-5.2996	550	14.9	25.3	6.2	485	117	216.5
<i>Q. suber</i>	3	68	39.4156	-5.2990	550	14.9	25.3	6.2	485	117	216.7

¹ For *Q. ilex*, Tiétar-Norte del Tajo (11a), Sierra de San Pedro-Guadalupe (11b), Tierra de Barros-La Serena (11d) and Sierra Morena Occidental (11e); for *Q. suber*, Sierra de San Pedro (2), Montes de Toledo (3) and Sierra Morena Occidental (5).

² MAT: mean annual temperature (°C)

³ MTWM: mean temperature of warmest month (°C)

⁴ MTCM: mean temperature of coldest month (°C)

⁵ MAP: mean annual precipitation (mm)

⁶ MSP: mean annual summer (May to September) precipitation (mm)

⁷ SHM: summer heat-moisture index, (MTWM)/(MSP/1000)

17 **Table S2.** REML estimates of genetic correlation coefficients ($r_g \pm$ s.e.) between seed weight, time to emerge, plant height, mortality and time to
 18 death variables described in Table 2 for *Quercus ilex* families. Associated significance levels of the log-likelihood ratio tests (ns, $\chi^2 > 0.05$; *, χ^2
 19 < 0.05 ; **, $\chi^2 < 0.01$; ***, $\chi^2 < 0.001$) of each genetic correlation are shown. Significant genetic correlations ($\chi^2 < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

	<i>Mortality 1</i>	<i>Mortality 2_D</i>	<i>Mortality 3</i>	<i>Mortality 3_D</i>	<i>Time to death 1</i>	<i>Time to death 1_D</i>	<i>Time to death 2</i>	<i>Time to death 2_D</i>
Seed weight	-0.61*** ± 0.09	-0.33 ± 0.21	-0.45* ± 0.18	-0.58*** ± 0.19	0.66*** ± 0.08	0.71*** ± 0.07	0.31 ± 0.22	0.67*** ± 0.16
Time to emerge	0.25 ± 0.01	-0.25 ± 0.53	0.42 ± 0.48	0.07 ± 0.57	-0.32 ± 0.32	-0.12 ± 0.32	-0.10 ± 0.52	0.10 ± 0.51
Plant height	-0.55*** ± 0.12	-0.21 ± 0.23	-0.30 ± 0.23	-0.11 ± 0.25	0.63*** ± 0.11	0.53*** ± 0.13	0.40*** ± 0.26	0.40*** ± 0.22

21

22 **Figure S1.** Rank changes of mortality (a) and time to death (b) of 66 *Quercus ilex*
23 families inoculated with *Phytophthora cinnamomi* in the absence (left axis) or presence
24 (right axis) of drought. Low rank indicates low mean mortality or early mean time to
25 death of seedlings from a particular family.